

Signalling Pathways in Myocardial Infarction: Drug Therapeutic Strategies and Molecular Insights into Isoproterenol-Induced Cardiac Damage

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Abstract- Myocardial infarction (MI) is still a global illness with a high morbidity and death rate, despite significant advancements in therapy. Even though there is a cure for myocardial infarction treatment, novel therapeutic strategies for cardio protection and cardiac repair are beginning to emerge. Evidence of pathological features in MI demonstrates cell signalling pathways involved in cardiomyocyte, endothelial cell, fibroblast, monocyte, and stem cell survival, proliferation, apoptosis, and autophagy. The signalling pathways plays major in all the pathological features. The major players in oxidative stress and apoptosis, such as Notch, Nrf2/HO-1 pathways and the main regulator of angiogenesis, MAPK, JAK/STAT pathways. These signalling pathways plays an important role in the pathogenesis of MI and targeting these pathways improves the pathological symptoms which is promising. The most widely used method for inducing MI in animal is isoproterenol induced myocardial infarction. It is non-invasive, rapid, simple method for producing myocardial damage in animal that is like MI seen in humans. In this review, we summarize the signalling pathways involved in myocardial infarction and the treatment approaches for MI by controlling these related pathways, which help to restore and reestablish injured hearts by reducing inflammation, preventing cardiomyocyte death, and promoting angiogenesis and the molecular mechanism involved in isoproterenol induced myocardial infarction.

Keywords: Signalling pathways, MI – Myocardial Infarction, ISO – Isoproterenol.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Cardiovascular diseases are the leading cause of death worldwide. These illnesses include a variety of conditions affecting the heart and blood arteries, such as deep vein thrombosis, pulmonary embolism, peripheral arterial and rheumatic heart diseases, coronary heart diseases, and cerebrovascular illnesses. At least 29% of fatalities worldwide in 2004 were attributed to CVDs, according to WHO estimates of 17.1 million deaths. By 2030, 23.6 million people are expected to receive a CVD diagnosis annually [1,3]. The primary cause of death from congestive heart failure (CHD) is myocardial infarction (MI), which is brought on by prolonged myocardial ischemia and myocyte necrosis as a result of a blood supply disruption to a portion of the heart.[2]

A very common condition is myocardial infarction (MI). Myocardial cells starving for oxygen, which is followed by an ischemia state that causes irreparable cardiac damage, which results in infarction. The left ventricles grow and dilate over time, making the cardiac muscles incapable of pumping oxygenated blood. This causes the arteries to narrow, starving the heart tissues of blood and ultimately leading to myocardial necrosis. Collagen subsequently replaces the necrotic myocyte cells. The hallmark of cardiac fibrosis is the thickening or scarring of the heart valves as a result of the disproportionate growth and buildup of cardiac fibroblasts, which deforms the heart's structure and impairs its mechanical operation. Type I and type III fibrillar collagen, which are important components of the cardiac interstitium, are synthesized by these fibroblasts. [4]

Targeting signaling pathways has been the focus of efforts over the past few decades to improve the prognosis following myocardial infarction (MI). These efforts include medication, gene therapy, protein therapy, cell therapy, and exosome treatment. These treatments target important signaling pathways to address the fundamental reasons of MI progression. [5,6,7] For instance, excessive inflammation and cardiac fibrosis are alleviated by blocking the TLR4/MyD88/nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) [8,9]. However, improving the activation of the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) and PI3K/Akt pathways encourages the development of functioning vasculatures [10]. In addition to the anti-fibrosis approach, other well-established and widely used treatments for MI include the anti-inflammation and therapeutic angiogenesis techniques that target molecular pathways. [11,12,13,14,15].

Based on the method of induction, preclinical models can be roughly divided into three groups: genetic, chemically, and surgically induced models. While doxorubicin and isoproterenol (ISP) are the main inducers used in chemically induced models, surgical models frequently result in considerable mortality and need highly skilled technical ability.

Doxorubicin induces oxidative stress in the heart, forming toxic adducts that lead to acute and frequently deadly cardiotoxicity. On the other hand, ISP can cause increasing heart damage when administered in fragmented doses or at higher levels to cause acute harm. One of the most researched and utilized models for both acute and chronic heart damage is ISP-induced cardiotoxicity. The screening of numerous plant-based products and their active ingredients has been done using this technique. [16].

In this review We go over the critical roles that these signalling pathways play in pathophysiological circumstances, as each of them presents a potential target for treatment in MI and molecular mechanism of isoproterenol induced cardiac damage.

2. MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION:

MI is described as an ischemia insult-induced death of cardiomyocytes. The diagnosis of MI depends on the sensitivity and specificity of the clinical criteria, electrocardiographic findings, imaging investigations, and biomarkers used to detect cardiomyocyte mortality, making its application in a clinical setting difficult.

Over the past few years, the identification of extremely sensitive biomarkers (such cardiac troponins) has substantially improved the clinician's capacity to identify cardiomyocyte mortality. It is important to note that while abrupt increases in circulating troponin levels are indicative of myocardial injury, they are not specific indicators of ischemic cardiomyocyte death. Instead, they may occasionally indicate increased cell wall permeability or the release of products that break down proteolytic troponin.[17]

The most common cause of acute myocardial infarction (MI), which results in an abrupt decrease in blood supply to the myocardium and ultimately causes heart failure and death, is a thrombus obstructing an artery or a bypass graft. [18,19]. In clinical settings thrombolysis, percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI), and coronary artery bypass grafting are the most often used treatments for acute MI [20,21,22]. The phases of inflammation, fibrosis, and angiogenesis in the damaged myocardium overlap after myocardial infarction [23,24].

2.1 PATHOGENESIS OF MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION:

Ischemia in a myocardial region is the initial cause of MI. Long-term ischemia causes the heart muscle to necrotize, which in turn causes reactive oxygen species (ROS) to build up [25]. ROS may cause issues related to ischemia-reperfusion, which may include CMC's death, once blood flow has been restored [26]. Numerous chemicals with signalling properties are released into the intercellular space because of the breakdown of CMC.

The infarct zone is cleared of injured cells and extracellular matrix (ECM) destruction during the inflammatory stage of MI. If the dead cell residues are successfully removed, the inflammation goes away, and the reparative phase starts. It entails revascularization, hypertrophy of the remaining CMC, fibroblast-produced collagen (scarring), and the replacement of deceased CMCs with fibroblasts to restore the structural integrity of the tissues [27]. Even in situations where perfusion is restored, fibrous scars develop because of the heart's inadequate capacity for regeneration [28]. Due to

- (1) decreased conduction between CMC (Cardiac Mesenchymal Cells) in the myocardium;
- (2) microvascular dysfunction; and
- (3) deposits of interstitial collagen,

which may stimulate proteases that break down the links between ECM (cardiac extracellular matrix) and CMC (Cardiac Mesenchymal Cells), this raises the risk of problems [28]. The Notch signalling pathway is one of the molecular interactions that underpin the regulation of events in MI.

3. SIGNALLING PATHWAYS INVOLVED IN MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AND ITS THERAPEUTIC STRATEGIES:

Cell signalling networks are essential for controlling these pathological circumstances. Notch, nuclear factor erythroid-derived 2-related factor 2/heme oxygenase-1 (Nrf2/HO-1), Ras homolog family member A/Rho-associated coiled-coil containing protein kinase (RhoA/ROCK), and Sonic hedgehog pathways are a few examples of cell signalling pathways that regulate cardiac regeneration, reactive fibrosis, and cardiac hypertrophy. They also mediate the survival, proliferation, apoptosis, differentiation, and other phenotypes of cells [29,30,31].

3.1 NOTCH SIGNALLING PATHWAY:

The gene that was first discovered in Thomas Hunt Morgan's lab to oversee the development of notches on *Drosophila melanogaster* wings is the source of the pathway's moniker, notch signalling [32]. Notch1 is extensively expressed in the immature myocardium during embryonic heart development and expressed at low levels in the postnatal myocardium. In adult hearts, the levels of Notch1, Hes1, and Jagged1 are extremely low at birth. Nonetheless, four days following myocardial infarction, their levels in cardiomyocytes are markedly elevated, indicating a potential role for the Notch signalling pathway in the control of myocardial damage [33]. Notch signalling, according to numerous studies, increases stem cell differentiation [34], encourages neovascularization [35], reduces myocardial fibrosis [36], and has numerous other beneficial effects [37]. These actions further mediate the healing of myocardial ischemia injury and enhance heart function [38]. Activating Notch signalling reduces the spectrum of myocardial ischemia and enhances

myocardial function following myocardial infarction, according to additional research [39]. Furthermore, data suggest that via enhancing angiogenesis [37,40,41] enhancing heart regeneration and cardio protection [37,42], and lowering fibrosis [36], apoptosis [43], and oxidative stress, the Notch pathway is linked to the amelioration of MI [37,44].

Jagged (JAG) or Delta-like (DLL) ligand attaches to the Notch receptor. The transcription of target genes then starts when the intracellular domain of the Notch receptor enters the nucleus and interacts with intracellular regulatory complexes. Mammals have been reported to possess four Notch receptors (1–4) and five canonical ligands (JAG1-2, DLL 1, 3, 4). Since they are all transmembrane proteins, the conventional Notch pathway cannot transmit signals without direct intercellular contacts [45]. It has just become evident how crucial Notch signalling is to the cardiovascular system. As a result, a mutation in the human NOTCH1 gene was identified in 2005, and it was then evident that several cardiovascular diseases were linked to abnormalities in the Notch signalling components [46]. It is now widely acknowledged that Notch plays a crucial role in the growth and operation of the cardiovascular system.

3.1.1 Angiogenesis enhanced by the Notch pathway.

Additionally, notch signaling affects the phenotypic and functional differentiation of endothelial cells in the circulatory system. Endothelial cells express Notch1, Notch4, Jagged1, DLL-1, and DLL-4; appropriate endothelial cell function can only be induced by proper ligand-receptor interaction.

In adult arteries, Notch1 functions as a mechanical sensor by converting mechanical stresses into intracellular impulses through endothelial cells [47]. Vascular homeostasis, junction integrity, and endothelial cell elongation all depend on intracellular signals [47]. In addition, the Notch pathway and VEGFA signalling are linked in the regulation of endothelial cell differentiation, capillary network sprouting, and endothelial tube branching and fusion [48].

3.1.2 The Notch pathway lowers the death of cardiomyocytes.

Studies conducted in vivo and in vitro have revealed that the Notch pathway is important in lowering cardiomyocyte apoptosis [43]. Notch1 controlled apoptosis in an in vitro study using a hypoxic cardiomyocyte model by upregulating caspase-9 and caspase-3 and downregulating Bcl-2 and Bax [43]. In MI mice, the Notch signalling system also controls the transcription factor RBP-J, which has an antiapoptotic effect [49]. Furthermore, a different study found that Notch1 reduces NF-KB's ability to bind to DNA, which has a negative regulatory effect on apoptosis inhibition and cell survival enhancement [50,51].

3.1.3 In cardiomyocytes, the Notch pathway lowers oxidative stress.

Numerous studies have documented the role of the Notch pathway in the prevention of oxidative stress [34,52,53]. For example, it has been shown that TNF- α inhibitors, in part through Notch1 signalling, decrease oxidative stress in cardiac ischemia/reperfusion (I/R) injury [52]. Because the Notch pathway is associated with antioxidative stress, scientists have created several therapeutic approaches and stem cells that increase Notch1 signalling to lower oxidative stress [34,53]. By upregulating the VEGF/Notch1/Jagged 1 axis, aldolase A (ALDOA) overexpression reduces oxidative stress and death in cardiomyocytes caused by hypoxia and reperfusion [53]. In vitro oxidative stress and ischemia injury reduced the death of endothelial cells and cardiomyocytes when EV-C-MSCs harbouring N1ICD were employed in another study [34].

3.2 JAK/STAT SIGNALLING PATHWAY IN MI:

The transfer of stimulation signals to the nucleus and subsequent promotion of gene transcription is directly attributed to cytokines, and this process is facilitated by the JAK/STAT signalling pathway. This route plays a major role in the occurrence and progression of many cardiovascular illnesses since it is extensively involved in cell stress responses, apoptosis, inflammation, and other biological processes [54]. The cytoplasmic tyrosine kinase JAK protein is connected to the intracellular domain of receptors that are attached to membranes [55]. Its job is to transfer signals to the nucleus from external ligands (such growth factors and cytokines) to synchronize cellular reactions [55]. The JAK family consists of four members (JAK1, JAK2, JAK3, and TYK2), while the STAT family has seven members (STAT1, STAT2, STAT3, STAT4, STAT5A, STAT5B, and STAT6) [56]. The JAK/STAT signalling pathway, also referred to as the IL-6 signalling pathway, is controlled by cytokines and is involved in numerous critical biological processes, such as immune regulation [57], cell division, apoptosis, and proliferation. It primarily regulates transmembrane receptors that communicate with the nucleus [58].

JAK/STAT controls nuclear communication and transmembrane receptors in four steps:

The process involves four steps: (1) cytokines binding to receptors causing receptor molecules to dimerize; (2) recruiting STAT protein to the docking site formed by these phosphorylated tyrosine sites; (3) activating and phosphorylating STATs, allowing them to dimerize; and (4) the STAT-STAT dimer translocating to the nucleus and controlling gene expression [59].

Figure 1: JAK/STAT pathway and focused treatment after myocardial infarction. JAK/STAT controls nuclear communication and transmembrane receptors in four steps: Receptor molecules dimerize as a result of cytokines binding to them, activating and phosphorylating JAKs; (2) STAT protein is drawn to the docking site these phosphorylated tyrosine sites form; (3) STATs are activated and phosphorylated, allowing them to dimerize; and (4) STAT–STAT dimer translocate to the nucleus and controls gene expression. JAK Janus kinase, EGCG (epigallocatechin-3-gallate), gp130 (glycoprotein 130), VEGF (vascular endothelial growth factor), Bcl-2 (b-cell lymphoma-2), and iNOS (inducible nitric oxide synthase) are examples of signal transduction and activator of transcription.

3.2.1 Myocardial apoptosis regulated by JAK/STAT signaling.

Cell apoptosis is one of the various forms and degrees of cell damage that have been found to be caused by an ischemic myocardium [60]. Prior research has mostly examined STAT1 and STAT3 in relation to the function of the JAK/STAT pathway in cardiac tissue [61]. For instance, after simulating the MI microenvironment, the supernatant of necrotic primary cardiomyocytes (Necrotic-S) activates the JAK1-STAT1 pathway and promotes the nuclear translocation of c-Fos and NF- κ B p53, further inducing hypoxia myocardial cell apoptosis [62]. However, STAT1 silencing inhibited the apoptosis of necrotic primary cardiomyocytes. Furthermore, by upregulating caspase 1, STAT1 is also found to trigger apoptosis in myocardial I/R [63]. STAT3 has an anti-apoptotic effect, in contrast to STAT1's pro-apoptotic effect [64]. The anti-apoptotic genes BCL-2 and p-STAT3 protein showed a considerable drop in expression in the rabbit I/R model. Following opioid receptor injection, there was a decrease in apoptotic cardiomyocytes and an increase in BCL-2 and p-STAT3 expression [65]. Additionally, following treatment with the JAK2 inhibitor AG-490, there was a significant decrease in the phosphorylation of STAT3 in the myocardium of rats suffering from MI, and a large increase in caspase-3 activity, Bax expression, and the quantity of apoptotic cells [66]. According to this research, the apoptotic response during myocardial infarction is strongly associated with the JAK/STAT system, and STAT1 and STAT3 appear to have opposing effects.

3.2.2 Modulator of cardiac cell death is STAT1

Following hypoxia/reoxygenation (H/R), cardiac myocytes exhibit elevated STAT1 phosphorylation, which exacerbates cardiac damage by inducing pro-apoptotic STAT1 effectors like caspase-1, FAS, and FASL [67]. When STAT1 is inhibited in cardiac myocytes, hypoxia/reoxygenation (H/R)-induced cell death is prevented. However, when IFN-alpha is used to extend STAT1 activity during reperfusion, the extent of the infarct increases, but this may be because to IFN-alpha's side effects [67,68]. In neuronal ischaemia, STAT1 has also been linked to a pro-apoptotic function. Mice lacking in STAT1 have less brain injury after I/R. This was linked to decreased neuronal cell death and caspase-3 activity [69]. Antioxidants' ability to protect the heart is linked to a decrease in STAT1 activity. Following I/R, the infarct size was reduced by the green tea polyphenol extract epigallocatechin-3-gallate and the free radical scavenger tempol, which also prevented STAT1 activation that was dependent on reperfusion [68,70]. It would be worthwhile to investigate whether these antioxidants' cardioprotective effects are still as strong in the presence of STAT1 deficiency. The pro-apoptotic effects of STAT1 in fibroblasts have been proposed to be counteracted by STAT3, and this may also apply to I/R-induced cell death in cardiac myocytes [73,67]. In cardiac myocytes, co-transfection of increasing quantities of STAT3 with STAT1 results in a dose-dependent decrease in STAT1-induced apoptosis after

ischaemia [67]. Interestingly, IL-6 causes prolonged activation of STAT1 and induces IFN-alpha like effects, such as the upregulation of major histocompatibility complex (MHC) class II molecules and the mounting of an antiviral response, even though STAT1 and STAT3 are activated by different ligands [71]. On the other hand, IFN-alpha causes STAT3 phosphorylation to increase and last longer in cells lacking STAT1 [71,72].

3.3 MAPK SIGNALLING PATHWAY IN MI:

Mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs) are a class of serine/threonine protein kinases that are highly conserved in cells and are involved in a three-level cascade signal transduction. ERK, c-JNK, p38/MAPK, and ERK5 are the four main branches of the MAPK signaling pathway that have been found thus far [74,75]. These kinases are progressively activated and together control numerous significant physiological and pathological effects, including the growth, differentiation, and proliferation of cardiac resident cells, including macrophages, endothelial cells, cardiomyocytes, and fibroblasts [76].

3.3.1 APOPTOSIS:

One of the most prominent characteristics that the MAPK signaling system mediates is apoptosis. Reduced cardiac function results from myocardial cell apoptosis following MI, but aggravating the formation of cardiac scarring following MI can be caused by non-myocardial cell death [77]. Thus, it makes sense to successfully prevent apoptosis by controlling the MAPK signaling pathway. This signaling pathway is the target of certain medicines. Kuanxiong aerosol works by blocking the MAPK signaling pathway, which prevents cardiac damage brought on by isoproterenol [78]. In post-MI mice, the well-known lipid-lowering medication atorvastatin dramatically enhances cardiac function and cardiomyocyte apoptosis; this effect is attributed to stimulation of the ERK1/2 signaling pathway [79]. It has been demonstrated that oxidative stress caused by ISO causes the overexpression of MAPK, primarily JNK and p38 MAPK, in the heart, which in turn causes apoptosis. Apoptosis is known to be induced by JNK and p38 MAPK, although ERK, another essential MAPK, is known to promote cell survival and is often downregulated in cases of acute myocardial ischemia. As a result, in the myocardium of rats given ISO treatment, we observed elevated levels of pro-apoptotic proteins (bax and caspase-3) and lower levels of ERK and anti-apoptotic protein (Bcl-2). We also detected upregulation of JNK and p38 MAPK. Conversely, a bioflavonoid therapy called Morin decreased the rate of apoptosis [80,81].

3.3.2 INFLAMMATION:

Following MI, the heart experiences inflammatory damage, and several inflammatory mediators are involved in the MI process. The degree of the inflammatory response also establishes the degree of MI, as does the ongoing pro-inflammatory response that follows MI and causes ventricular remodelling [82]. Targeted intervention in the MAPK signaling pathway, which is linked to the inflammatory phenotype, improves the prognosis of acute myocardial infarction (AMI) by preventing inflammation from starting and spreading [83]. The cardioprotective impact of Osthole, an active ingredient in *Cnidium monnieri* extract, was assessed in AMI by Duan et al. Researchers discovered that Osthole alleviates rats' post-myocardial infarction symptoms via activating the MAPK pathway to reduce the expression of inflammatory cytokines [84]. Rats' myocardial necrosis caused by isoproterenol is resisted by the bioflavonoid morin. The findings showed that p-JNK, P38, p-ERK1/2 protein levels and associated inflammatory indices (TNF- α and IL-6) were altered, suggesting that morin regulates the MAPK pathway to lower inflammatory indicators and protect against myocardial damage [81].

3.3.3 ANGIOGENESIS:

Theoretically, more blood vessels supplying ischemic tissue could result in richer blood flow in MI [85]. By promoting angiogenesis through this mechanism, MI patients may fare better. One kind of traditional Chinese medicine used to treat cardiovascular conditions is called danhong injection. Li et al. discovered that after treating MI mice with Danhong injection in vivo and in vitro, the infarct area was greatly lowered, the capillary density increased [86], and the proliferation and migratory ability of Human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) was significantly improved [87].

3.4 TLR4/MYD88/NF-KB-SIGNALING PATHWAY IN MI:

TLRs are innate immune sensing receptors that identify invasive pathogens' PAMPs and, by controlling different parallel sequential adapter-kinase complexes, initiate signaling cascades [88]. Numerous protein kinases, such as mitogen-activated kinase-like protein (MAPK) and interleukin-1 receptor-associated kinases (IRAK), are activated by TLR signaling [89]. TLRs independently recruit various members of the TIRAP (TIR domain-containing adaptor protein) family, including TIRAP/MAL, MyD88, TRAM, TIR domain-containing adapter-inducing interferon- β (TRIF), and TRAM. They also start signaling cascades [90]. Two primary routes, MyD88 and TIRAP, which initiate the interferon- β -dependent pathway, are responsible for TLR activation. MyD88 activation causes TLR2, TLR4, TLR7, and TLR9 to bind with cytoplasmic Toll/interleukin-1 receptor-like protein (TIR). This attachment triggers TLR signaling by increasing I-kappa B kinase beta (IKK β) activity, which is then followed by phosphorylation and IKK complex disintegration. As a result, transcription factor NF- κ B (nuclear factor kappa B) is translated nuclearly, starting the synthesis of inflammatory cytokines [91]. Apart from TLR3, every TLR uses the MyD88-dependent pathway. Additionally, the TRIF-dependent pathway activates IRF3, NF- κ B, and interferon regulatory factor-3 (IRF3), which

makes it possible to produce interferon- α and interferon- β as well as inflammatory cytokines. TLR4 also activates IRF3 and binds the adaptor proteins TRIF and TRAM. MyD88-independent TLR3 and TLR4 play a key role in TLR-mediated NF- κ B activation [92].

Figure 2

Figure 2: Shows the function of inflammatory cytokines and TLR activation in MI. MyD88 and TRIF control the synthesis of inflammatory cytokines and start signaling cascades via the NF- κ B/interferon- β -dependent pathway. Increased inflammatory cytokine levels are linked to cardiac injury and stress. TLR-targeting techniques, however, might be a useful treatment for MI. Toll-like receptors (TLRs); pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs); damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs); myeloid differentiation primary response gene (MyD88); TIR domain-containing adapter-inducing interferon- β); nuclear factor-kappa B (NF- κ B); interferon regulatory factors (IRFs); interleukin (IL); and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF α).

Following myocardial infarction, the TLR4/MyD88/NF- κ B signaling pathway regulates inflammation, pyroptosis, apoptosis, fibrosis, ventricular arrhythmias, and lipid metabolism. TLR4/MyD88/NF- κ B regulation in MI is mediated by certain molecules or transcription factors. Using the TLR4/MyD88/NF- κ B signaling pathway, *Gentiana acuta*, astaxanthin, astragaloside IV, and danshen (*Salvia miltiorrhiza*) may reduce inflammatory damage following acute MI [93,94]. Conversely, Li et al. reported that the TLR4/MyD88/NF- κ B/NLRP3 signalling pathway was involved in reducing pyroptosis in MI rats given nicorandil treatment [95]. Rat apoptosis is also lessened when the dapson-mediated cardio protection pathway, which inhibits the TLR4/TNF- α signalling pathway, is activated [96]. Furthermore, through modified citrus pectin, the TLR4/MyD88/NF- κ B pathway has a unique role in ameliorating cardiac fibrosis [97].

3.5 ROLE OF NRF2/HO-1 SIGNALING PATHWAY IN MI:

The NFE2L2 gene produces NRF2, which has seven functional domains [98]. It belongs to the Cap 'n' Collar (CNC) subfamily [99]. In a state without stress, NRF2 is incredibly unstable and quickly deteriorates [100]. NRF2 (nuclear factor erythroid-derived 2-related factor 2) is an essential factor that maintains ROS homeostasis and contributes to the regulation of antioxidant genes [101]. It could detect oxidative stimuli and send signaling molecules to the nucleus, whereupon it would start the transcription of antioxidant genes [102]. The use of NRF2-activated drugs efficiently lowers ROS in acute kidney damage, stroke, and other disorders, avoiding or delaying the progression of the disease [103,104].

The enzyme heme oxygenase (HO) catalyzes the conversion of heme to iron, carbon monoxide (CO), and biliverdin IX α . It is a rate-limiting enzyme [105]. The three isoenzymes that make up the HO system, HO-1, HO-2, and HO-3, all exhibit the same catalytic activity [106]. HO-1 is implicated in oxidative stress and cell protection as a downstream

target of NRF2. For instance, HO-1 guards against I/R damage to liver cells [108], hippocampus neurons [109], and retinal ganglion cells [107]. Furthermore, HO-1 can enter mitochondria to control cell inflammation and autophagy [110]. Consequently, it is important to consider HO-1's protective role on myocardial cells following MI.

3.5.1 APOPTOSIS:

Nearly every type of cell in the body has the NRF2/HO-1 pathway, which is crucial for preserving homeostasis and lowering oxidative stress [111]. One of the primary causes of cardiac function impairment following MI is myocardial cell apoptosis [112]. Research has demonstrated that low-dose carvedilol in conjunction with wogonin [113], hirudin [114], dapsone [96], and rosuvastatin [115] all work on the NRF2/HO-1 pathway to prevent oxidative stress damage to cardiomyocytes during MI and to lower cardiomyocyte apoptosis. In the end, ventricular remodeling is avoided while maintaining normal cardiomyocyte activity and myocardial tissue shape. By preventing NF- κ B and AP-1 from translocating, HO-1 inhibits myocardial apoptosis when it is successfully activated in rabbit I/R models [116].

Additionally, myocardial apoptosis and the extent of MI were greatly decreased by pre-injecting HO-1 or HO-1 activator into the heart. According to all the available data, HO-1 can directly cure MI by minimizing damage brought on by oxidative stress [117,118].

3.5.2 Oxidative stress:

By controlling ion channels, NRF2/HO-1 also shields cardiomyocytes from oxidative stress. Cellular oxidative stress and dysfunction are caused by the activation of Ca²⁺-dependent degradation enzymes, which is triggered by an excess of Ca²⁺ input. The result of HO-1 breaking down heme is carbon monoxide, which blocks both T- and L-type Ca²⁺ channels to shield cardiomyocytes and encourage the growth of VSMCs [119,120].

Mitochondria and ion channel function are intimately linked. Overabundance ROS are deposited, and the mitochondrial membrane potential becomes dysfunctional in cardiomyocytes that are ischemic [121].

4. THERAPEUTIC STRATEGY

4.1 DRUG THERAPIES:

- By boosting autophagy function, ivabradine significantly rescued rats from heart damage following myocardial infarction. Iva's inhibition of the PI3K/AKT/mTOR/p70S6K signalling pathways transduction could be one of the possible mechanisms at play. The preclinical data from this investigation may support the use of ivabradine to treat MI. Dai et al. 2021 [122]
- Everolimus, an mTOR inhibitor prevents Left ventricular Remodelling after MI. The targeting pathway involved in this is PI3K/Akt/mTOR Buss et al. 2009 [123]
- The cardioprotective effects of sphingosine-1-phosphate (S1P)/S1P receptor 1 signaling include the suppression of myocyte death. Following MI, S1P therapy reduces mTOR activity, improves myocyte autophagy, and prevents LV remodeling. Yang et al. 2021 [124]
- A TNF-inhibitor guards against myocardial ischemia/reperfusion (MI/R) damage. In inflammatory bowel illness, it can also raise Notch1 expression, exposing the control of TNF- α inhibitor on Notch1 signaling. TNF-inhibitor-mediated regulation of oxidative/nitrative stress is one way whereby Notch1 signaling mediates the reduction of MI/R damage. Pei et al. 2015 [52]
- The potential therapeutic targets for treating MI could be HIF- α , Notch1, and Jagged1 signaling upregulation, as evidenced by the cardioprotective effects of astragaloside against myocardial injury after MI. Yu et al. 2017 [125]
- Myocardial vascular endothelium growth factor (VEGF), which is linked to adenosine release, was expressed more when LDE-MTX was administered. This was correlated not only with an increase in angiogenesis but also with other parameters that LDE-MTX improved, indicating that the increase in VEGF was a significant factor in LDE-MTX's positive effects. Future clinical trials are supported by the impressive increase in cardiac function and reduction in infarction size attained by LDE-MTX. Maranhão et al. 2017 [126]
- One of *Scutellaria radix*'s primary active components is a type of flavonoid molecule called wogonin. In addition to markedly upregulating the protein expression of nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor (Nrf2) and heme oxygenase-1 (HO-1), pre-treatment with Wog np (25 and 50 mg/kg) could significantly reduce the size of cardiac infarcts, serum cardiac markers, lipid peroxidation product (MDA), and inflammatory markers. This would confer its strong cardioprotective activity against ISO-induced myocardial damage. Bei et al. 2020 [113]
- Hirudin attenuated reactive oxygen species (ROS), malondialdehyde (MDA), and superoxide dismutase (SOD) to achieve its cardioprotective effect. By upsetting the Keap1-Nrf2 complex, it caused the activation of the Nuclear Factor Erythroid 2 Related Factor 2 (Nrf2) signal pathway. As a result, Nrf2 moved from the cytoplasm to the nucleus to control the expression of Nrf2-dependent genes (HO-1, SOD). Moreover, it should be mentioned that hirudin not only prevented apoptosis linked to cytochrome C, but also restored mitochondrial membrane potential. Zhang et al. 2020 [114]

- By significantly reducing the extent of the myocardial infarct and suppressing oxidative stress, inflammation, and apoptosis through the up-regulation of the Nrf2/HO-1 and TLR4/TNF- α signaling pathways, Dapsone demonstrated effective ameliorative activities against ISO-caused MI. Abdelzaher et al. 2021 [96]
- It has been demonstrated that rosuvastatin activates the PI3K/Akt/Nrf2/HO-1 pathway, which enhances myocardial cell survival. In addition to preventing the ECG and histological changes brought on by ISP, treatment with modest doses of rosuvastatin and carvedilol significantly decreased the levels of C-reactive protein, cardiac troponin-I, creatine kinase-MB, infarct size, and heart index when compared to the ISP group. Combination therapy outperforms monotherapy in the most examined parameters, possibly because it activates the pro-survival Nrf2/HO-1 pro-survival signaling pathway PI3K/Akt. Baraka et al. 2021 [115]
- Strong antioxidant properties of coptisine allow it to prevent the overexpression of RhoA/ROCK in response to high-dose isoproterenol treatment, minimize apoptosis in cardiac cells, improve respiratory dysfunction in mitochondria, and preserve the integrity of cell membranes. As coptisine demonstrated cardioprotection in a myocardial infarction model, it merits consideration as a potential supplementary treatment to mitigate myocardial damage. Gong et al. 2012 [127]
- After MI, DHI therapy increased post-infarct angiogenesis by triggering the miR-126/ERK/VEGF pathway. For patients who had an infarction, the current study offered a cutting-edge therapy plan. The usefulness of DHI as an adjunctive treatment for cardiac rehabilitation after MI requires more research. Li et al. 2019 [87]
- By stimulating the JAK/STAT pathway, IL33 not only suppressed cardiac apoptosis and decreased the early inflammatory response, but it also raised the number of M2 macrophages in the infarcted area, greatly decreased the infarct area, and stopped the progression of fibrosis. Consequently, for myocardial infarction, IL33 might represent a novel cardiac protective cytokine. Li et al. 2019 [128]
- PEDF therapy stimulates the nitric oxide pathway, and CCMR remodeling is facilitated by the Notch-1 pathway. After an acute myocardial infarction, increasing native collateral blood flow can aid in the remodeling of the ventricles and enhance prognosis. Liu et al. 2019 [129]
- The downregulation of Bcl-2 expression and the up-regulation of caspase-3 and Bax expression brought on by ISO were both significantly lowered by KXA. RNA sequencing revealed that following KXA therapy, 90 up-regulated genes caused by ISO were down-regulated, and 27 down-regulated genes induced by ISO were up-regulated. Furthermore, mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) signaling pathway may be a major target of KXA in the therapy of ISO-induced MI in rats, according to KEGG pathway enrichment study. Western blot examination supported the RNA sequencing data, which demonstrated that KXA markedly reduced the activation of the ISO-induced MAPK pathway. Lu et al. 2021 [130]

5. ISOPROTERENOL INDUCED MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION:

Previously myocardial infarction was performed through many surgical procedures such as

- Aorta binding
- Infusion of beta adrenergic via implanted osmotic mini pumps
- Coronary artery ligation

Because of these surgical procedures there is high chance of mortality and morbidity rate [131,132]. To evaluate the effect of substances in myocardial injury, this model of induction of MI by isoproterenol in rats given its effectiveness, reliability of animals and continuously performed in international studies. Isoproterenol administration in animal is a rapid, simple, non-invasive method which mimics similar Myocardial infarction seen in humans. Isoproterenol is a synthetic sympathomimetic nonselective beta-adrenergic agonist used to treat bradycardia and heart block [133]. A single subcutaneous administration of ISO (85mg/kg s.c) can produce Myocardial necrosis, myocardial fibrosis and repeated administration increase the injury of myocardium [131]. Isoprenaline produces infarct-like lesion like human MI. Isoprenaline-induced MI method has been used widely in the research on the protective effect of the natural product that can prevent myocardial necrosis damage in the animal likes mice, rats, and rabbits [134].

Metabolic pathway analysis was applied to know the pathways involved in the development of MI. Five disturbed metabolic pathways are Taurine and hypotaurine metabolism Glycolysis, arachidonic acid metabolism, Glycine, serine, threonine and histidine metabolism

Histamine, taurine, arachidonic acid, threonine, 3-methylhistamine, glucose-1-phosphate, glycine and glucose are the five key pathways may denote their potential as targeted biomarkers related to MI. This analysis showed that ISO influenced the abnormal metabolism of pathways, and the result of myocardial damage is due to the following which includes inflammation, deficiency of energy metabolism in the respective pathophysiological processes [135].

Figure 3: shows the Physiological effects of isoproterenol on myocardium

6. MOLECULAR MECHANISM OF ISOPROTERENOL INDUCED MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION:

Subcutaneous administration of isoproterenol causes damage to myocardium with biochemical and histological changes. The isoproterenol administration results in oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation. Further increase in oxidative stress results in release of leukotrienes, reactive oxygen species, hydrolytic enzyme which causes more damage to myocardium [132]. In myocardium the tissue defence system consists of antioxidant enzymes including catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione (GSH), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) [136]. SOD and CAT plays a major role in protecting cell against oxidative stress by catalytical removal of superoxide radicals and conversion to hydrogen peroxide. This isoproterenol causes significant decrease in SOD and CAT causing oxidative stress and impairs mitochondrial energy required for normal cardiac function. GSH protects the cell from reactive oxygen species by scavenging reactive oxygen species and neutralising them. GPx also protects cellular domain from peroxidative damage. This levels of antioxidants catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione (GSH), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) significantly gets reduced by isoproterenol causing myocardial injury. This increased oxidative stress also rises the level of malondialdehyde (MDA) [137].

Cardiac markers are the useful for detection of myocardial damage having great clinical importance. The levels of myocardial injury markers like aspartate transaminase [AST], troponin I [TnI], lactate dehydrogenase [LDH], creatine kinase [CK-MB], creatine phosphokinase [CPK-MB], serum glutamic- oxaloacetic transaminase [SGOT], and serum glutamic-pyruvic transaminase [SGPT] and pro-inflammatory cytokines (C-reactive protein [CRP], interleukin-6 [IL-6], and tumor necrosis factor- α [TNF- α]) increases with Isoproterenol administration in progression with necrosis of myocardium. SGOT, CK-MB and Troponin I are the early markers for detection of myocardial injury and LDH is a delayed marker of Myocardial Infarction which begins to rise in 12–24 hours which rises to peak level in 2 to 3 days. The cell membrane integrity gets disrupted due to lack of oxygen and glucose which results in leakage of these enzymes (SGOT, TnI, LDH and CPK-MB). The serum levels of Troponin I gets increased which is mainly associated with myocardial injury. The inflammatory markers like IL-6, CRP and TNF alpha gets increased which plays a major role in myocardial injury [137]. Reactive oxygen species intermediates cause damage to cellular DNA activating pathways of stress response. This injury initiates cytokine mediated cascade which produces tumor necrosis factor alpha. This overexpression of TNF alpha stimulates TNF alpha receptor type 1 inducing

- Contractile dysfunction
- Cardiac hypertrophy
- Cardiac fibrosis
- Cell death

The potent stimulator of inflammation is the increase in intracellular Ca^{2+} with generation of calcium pyrophosphate complexes and formation of uric acid. ISO administration also produces Ca^{2+} ions overloaded causing the depletion of ATP levels. The Ca^{2+} accumulation affects the mitochondrial membrane potential results in ROS formation damages the DNA by fragmentation leading to cellular apoptosis [132,137]. Cellular apoptosis results in downregulation of

antiapoptotic protein bcl-2 and pro-apoptotic protein Bax. The alteration produced by ISO in heart are similar to alteration taking place in human MI [138].

7. CONCLUSION:

The impact of the cellular and molecular levels in MI pathogenic processes as well as the treatment procedures have been considered in the developing therapeutic techniques over the past few decades. Studies aimed at addressing molecular signalling after myocardial infarction and ischemia, both preclinical and clinical, have shown encouraging results. In this review, the most important signalling pathways for treating MI and the molecular mechanisms causing isoproterenol-induced myocardial infarction were thoroughly identified and summarized.

Notch, TLR4/MyD88/NF- κ B, Nrf2/HO-1, MAPK, JAK/STAT, and other key signalling pathways are discussed here. These pathways are primarily focused on different pathological states, such as inflammation, oxidative stress, fibrosis, hypertrophy, apoptosis, survival, angiogenesis, and regeneration after MI [139,140]. Amazingly, rather of functioning independently, these combine to form an advanced and homeostatic regulatory network. It should be noted in this context that innovative medicines that influence pathways may have a greater positive impact on heart repair and MI secondary prevention. Some of the therapeutic strategies of the drug targeting signalling pathways have been discussed. Isoproterenol induced myocardial infarction is one of the widely used animal model with low mortality and morbidity rate. Although the exact mechanism underlying ISP-induced cardiotoxicity is unknown, it is thought to produce extremely cytotoxic free radicals in myocytes that, upon auto-oxidation, cause necrosis and death. Molecular insights of the ISO induced myocardial infarction has been discussed and summarized and it is one of the most convenient methods.

Determining the targeted therapy procedures for MI development requires characterization of the transduction and control of signalling pathways. This information will aid in the investigation and implementation of innovative therapeutic approaches for MI, as we have thoroughly examined the roles of signalling pathways in the pathological development and treatment of MI, as well as the future research direction of myocardial infarction treatment.

ABBREVIATIONS:

CVD – cardiovascular diseases

CHF - Congestive heart failure

MI – Myocardial Infarction

ROS – Reactive oxygen species

ECM - Cardiac Extracellular Matrix

CMC- Cardiac Mesenchymal Cells

JAK – Janus Kinases,

STAT – Signal Transducer and Activator of Transcription Proteins

Nuclear Factor Erythroid 2-related factor (Nrf2) Transcription factor/Hemoxygenase 1 (HO-1)

MAPK - Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinases

VEGF - Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor

EGCG - Epigallocatechin-3-Gallate)

TLR4, toll-like receptor 4; MyD88, myeloid differentiation primary response 88;

NF- κ B - Nuclear Factor κ B

PI3K - Phosphoinositide-3-kinase

TLR - Toll-like receptors

PAMPs - Pathogen-associated molecular patterns

DAMPs - Damage-associated molecular patterns

MyD88 - Myeloid Differentiation primary response gene

HUVECs - Human umbilical vein endothelial cells

mTOR - The mechanistic target of rapamycin

ERK - Extracellular signal-regulated kinases

JNK- the c-Jun N-terminal kinases

IRFs - Interferon Regulatory Factors

IL - Interleukin

TNF α - Tumor Necrosis Factor- α

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